

Scatter plots of medical students' total quarter-life crisis score and Big Five personality trait scores

Simple Scatter with Fit Line of QLC total by conscientiousness

Simple Scatter with Fit Line of QLC total by emotional stability

Simple Scatter with Fit Line of QLC total by Intellect/imagination

